

“Being an early adopter of publishing openly has been very beneficial to my career”

Adema says there shouldn't be any barriers to accessing research. Nor does she believe in waiting to put a finished product out there.

When it's suitable and appropriate, she believes in open practice throughout the research lifecycle, from the initial conception of a research idea and the planning stages, data collection and sourcing information, through to analysis and publication.

An early blogger, she has regularly invited others to collaborate with her and engage with her work as it progresses.

She explained: “Communicating my research is something I've always done, right from the start of my academic career. I've always put as much as possible on my blog and shared it – my work in progress, my research presentations, my conference presentations and my papers.

Janneke Adema,
Associate Professor in
Digital Media
at The Centre for
Postdigital Cultures,
Coventry University

How publishing open access benefits Adema

Highly visible and transparent approach creates a buzz

Collaborative approach engages other researchers

Raises profile early in your career

Bigger and broader reach for your work

Breaks down barriers to your work